

WP5 – PED Case Studies

Task 5.1 – Case studies selected

Deliverable D5.1 – Selected case studies available

Authorship & responsibility of WP5:

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Overview of WP5

PED case studies

WP5 connects our research with real-world challenges by applying the synthesized framework from WP1-4 to urban case studies in Switzerland, Austria, France, and the Netherlands.

PED case studies in Zurich (CH), Dübendorf (CH), Vienna (AT) & Groningen (NL)

WP5 is the application phase of the project, where the integrated model developed in WP4 is employed in real-world settings, specifically focusing on PEDs in Zurich and Dübendorf, Switzerland, Groningen, the Netherlands and Vienna, Austria. Through ICLEI, a city from Germany and Eastern Europe (e.g., Budapest, Hungary; Ljubljana, Slovenia; Taurage, Lithuania; or Warsaw, Poland) could also be included. This work package will test the practicality and effectiveness of the model, providing vital insights into its applicability in diverse urban contexts. The potential benefit of PEDs for the case studies will be quantified through modelling as well. Extensive data collection processes will be launched covering current energy usage patterns, local policy frameworks, socio-economic demographics, and urban infrastructure details. In the process of data collection and application, close collaboration with our urban governance partners will be sought to ensure that the model addresses real-world challenges and opportunities, and the findings are grounded in local realities.

Milestone 5: Integrated model applied on various districts in case study cities.

The following pages will provide general information and brief descriptions of the selected case studies covered within the project.

Quartier Baumgarten

Location	1140 Vienna, Austria
Area	ca. 700.000m ²
Date	1949-N/A
Usage	Residential, Commercial, Office, Transport & Logistics
Buildings	approx. 180

Description:

The Baumgarten district in Vienna's 14th municipal district was selected as one of three pilot zones for the "Pioneer City – Partnership for Climate-Neutral Cities 2030" mission. Covering 70 hectares with 180 buildings, the area includes diverse structures such as a football stadium, a historic social housing complex, a railway station, single-family homes, a school, offices, and a logistics center. This five-year public-public cooperation (2023–2028) aims to accelerate climate neutrality by 2030 through administrative process adaptation, energy and mobility transition pilots, and the creation of a nationwide learning environment. Key agendas for Baumgarten include developing an innovative heating network, implementing cost-effective energy solutions, and testing new business models, positioning the district as a blueprint for future climate-neutral urban development in Vienna.

Net Zero Pilot District

Location	Zurich, Switzerland
Area	Binz / Alt-Wiedikon
Date	2025-2031
Use	Residential and Commercial/Industrial
Buildings	NA

Description:

The Pilotquartier Netto-Null is an ambitious six-year initiative launched by the City of Zurich to advance its goal of achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2040. Taking place in the Binz / Alt-Wiedikon district from 2025 to 2031, the project acts as a real-world laboratory to test, evaluate, and scale innovative climate protection strategies at the neighborhood level. The selected area is diverse, encompassing residential, commercial, industrial, and educational zones. It is home to approximately 9,000 residents and hosts around 14,000 workplaces. This heterogeneity provides a rich environment for experimenting with various climate actions and stakeholder engagement approaches. The project combines top-down and bottom-up measures, supporting both municipal initiatives and citizen-led actions. Key areas of focus include the decarbonization of heating, the expansion of solar energy, sustainable mobility, and circular economy practices. A dedicated CHF 7.7 million budget supports project coordination, participation, communication, evaluation, and seed funding for local initiatives. The project is structured into a preparatory phase (2024–2025), an implementation phase (2025–2031), and includes a midterm and final evaluation.

De Hoogte

Location	Groningen, the Netherlands
Area	570.000m ²
Date	around 1920
Use	Residential (4140 inhabitants)
Buildings	2599

Description:

The neighborhood De Hoogte is located within the district Oud-Noord in the municipality of Groningen. The most common postal code in the neighborhood De Hoogte is 9716.

There are 2,719 addresses and 2,605 homes in the neighborhood De Hoogte in the municipality of Groningen. 91% of the homes in the neighborhood are rental properties. The homes have an average property value (WOZ) of €225,000. There are 4,140 residents in the neighborhood De Hoogte, with the largest age group (44%) being between 25 and 45 years old. The neighborhood has 2,760 households, with an average household size of 1.5 people. Additionally, there are 1,095 passenger cars and 430 business establishments registered in the neighborhood. The total area of De Hoogte is 57 hectares, of which 55 hectares is land and 2 hectares is water (100 hectares equals one square kilometer, or 1 km²). The average address density is 5,328 addresses per km²

Source: [Buurt De Hoogte \(gemeente Groningen\) in cijfers en grafieken | AlleCijfers.nl](#)